

Missions San Xavier del Bac

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A 17th-century Catholic mission established by the Jesuit priest, Father Eusebio Kino. The current mission, constructed between 1783 and 1797, is located on the Tohono O'odham Nation San Xavier Indian Reservation and still serves the nearby Indigenous population to this day. It is the oldest European structure in Arizona.

Date Range: 1692 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Tohono O'odham Nation San Xavier Indian Reservation

Region tags: United States, Arizona

The Tohono O'odham Nation San Xavier Indian Reservation is located in the state of Arizona, in the Southwest region of the United States of America. It is part of the Tucson metropolitan area in Pima County.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Cheek, Annetta L. The Evidence of Acculturation in Artifacts: Indians and Non-Indians at San Xavier del Bac, Arizona.
- Source 2: Umberger, Emily. A Tale of Two Saints.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.sanxaviermission.org/>
- Source 1 Description: San Xavier Mission
- Source 2 URL: <https://web.archive.org/web/20081228120816/http://tps.cr.nps.gov/nhl/detail.cfm?ResourceId=103&ResourceType=Building>
- Source 2 Description: Register of National Historic Landmarks
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.newadvent.org/cathen/13464b.htm>

– Source 3 Description: New Advent - San Xavier Mission page

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: Excavations were carried out by several archaeologists, including William J. Robinson and Annetta L. Cheek.

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1957-1974

Notes: Excavations were not carried out every year, but rather over several field seasons throughout this time period.

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Ariz.AA:16:10

Notes: Also known as San Xavier del Bac

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Body of water (as distinct from source)

Notes: Santa Cruz River

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Trackway or road-surface

– Plantings

– Other [specify]: Nearby towns, highway 1-19, and other features associated with human settlement in the pre-contact, colonial, and modern-day periods.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Notes: Although close to nearby communities, the city of Tucson, and a modern highway, it is contained within its own complex.

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

A single structure

– No

One single feature

– Purposefully placed plants

Notes: There is a garden.

A group of structures:

– Yes

Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: There is an active school, gardens, and a convent for the nuns.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

–Other [specify]: Communal and individual worship as well as a pilgrimage site.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: Renovations began in 1992 and were still continuing as of 2021.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

–Other [specify]: Multiple methods of destruction including burning and intentional collapse.

Notes: Different buildings were destroyed during various periods of revolt by local Indigenous. For example, in 1751 the house of the padre and the chapel were destroyed during a revolt by the Piman.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

- For religious reasons
- For economic reasons
- For political reasons
- As the result of war

Notes: Buildings were destroyed during various periods of revolt by local Indigenous peoples.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

- Natural phenomena

Notes: The mortuary wall and part of the church were damaged by an earthquake in 1887. In 1939, the West Tower was hit by a lightning strike.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

- Yes

↳ In antiquity

- More than once

↳ In modernity

- Post-Renaissance

Notes: Repairs were made beginning in 1909 after an earthquake damaged parts of the church in 1887. After 1939 there was further restoration to repair damage from a lightning strike. Further renovations began in 1992 and continued up through today.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

- Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

- Yes [specify]: Catholic God, Holy Trinity, and associated saints and other figures.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

- No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

- No

Notes: Depends on how one views the Holy Trinity and associated saints.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

– Religious specialists affiliated with political entity

Notes: The Spanish Crown and Jesuit order. Currently administered by the Franciscan order.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Corvee labourers

– Men

– Women

Notes: The Tohono O'odham

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: Father Kino's proselytization to the O'odham Indigenous peoples of the area.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Notes: Funds from colonial enterprises, the Catholic Church, and Spanish Crown.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

–Other [specify]: Proselytization to the Indigenous peoples and conversion.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: There is a attached school and a convent.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 75

Notes: Aside from the church and associated religious buildings, there is also a garden.

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 683

Notes: This is a measurement of the transept only. The nave measures 8.2 meters, but no width dimension is given.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 16

Notes: Measure of cupola above the transept.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

Notes: The other associated features are of various sizes.

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Notes: The heights of the associated features/structures vary.

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– I don't know

Notes: Possibly in earlier construction phases

↳ Sand

– I don't know

Notes: Possibly used in creation of other building materials.

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Yes

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Lime mortar

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Some metal used in the construction, restoration, renovations, and decoration.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: Moorish-inspired white stucco and carved mesquite doors.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: Paintings, carvings, frescoes, and statues.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Decoration is attached to the building's exterior but is not movable. Some of decorations, such as the statues, are movable.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– I don't know

Notes: I have not been there in some time and cannot recall if the Catholic God is depicted. No specific mention of God is mentioned in the sources. However, the Nazarene Christ is depicted on the interior.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Several saints, the Nazarene Christ, and Joseph and Mary.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Shells are repeated throughout and there are also a lot of Baroque architectural features.

Notes: The shell motif is a symbol of pilgrimage related to the patron saint of Spain, Santiago (James the Greater). The Baroque features include faux doors and theatrical curtain displays.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

Notes: Dedicated to the Virgin Mary and various saints.

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The Nazarene Christ.

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: Various saints, the Virgin Mary, the Nazarene Christ, and Joseph.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Symbols representing the Sacrament of the Communion and the union of the Christ and St. Francis of Assisi. These symbols would have only been recognized and understood by the Franciscans and not by the Indigenous congregants.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: St. Francis of Assisi receiving the stigmata.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: The Sacrament of the Communion and the relationship between the Christ and St. Francis of Assisi.

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: Various saints, the Nazarene Christ, the Virgin Mary, and Joseph.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: The Sacrament of Communion and the relationship between the Christ and St. Francis of Assisi.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– I don't know

Notes: In a sense, the saints are dead as are the other religious figures present in the church.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– Yes

Notes: There is a mortuary chapel and a cemetery.

Cremation:

– No

Notes: While interments may be cremated, they are not cremated on site.

Mummification:

– No

Interment:

– Yes

Notes: There is a cemetery.

Cannibalism:

– No

Exposure to the elements:

– No

Feeding to animals:

– No

Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (time/resources expended) treatment [Specify]:

–Other [specify]: Catholic rites for the deceased.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– I don't know

Notes: Depends on the wishes of the deceased's family.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– I don't know

Notes: Some families may have a larger mausoleum.

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– I don't know

Notes: Depends on what you believe about the nature of God.

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: According to Catholic mythology, God lives in the heavens above the earth.

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

–Other [specify]: N/A

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: Through prayer during church services.

↳ In dreams:

– No

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– I don't know

Notes: If you want to count Catholic rites as divination practices.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– I don't know

Notes: Yes and no.

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Notes: But this would also depend on an individual practitioner's beliefs. They may feel that a relative's spirit is present because they are buried nearby.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: Depends on the individual practitioner's beliefs.

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– I don't know

Notes: Depends on how you view the Holy Trinity, but there is a statue of the Nazarene Christ.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: Concern about the sexual morality of practitioners, but this is self-enforced.

↳ Does the worship include sex acts/references:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: N/A

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: Practitioners and pilgrims communicate with God, Jesus, the Virgin Mary, and the various saints through prayer and Catholic rites.

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Catholic rites by the priest

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Catholic rites by the individual practitioner

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Members of the congregation

↳ How often do these rituals take place:
– specify: Mass takes place on specific days, sometimes several times a day.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
– Yes
Notes: The priest follows the Catholic rites.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
– Yes
Notes: The Catholic priest correctly performs the rights as do the individual practitioners.

↳ Are there synchronic practices:
– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
– No
Notes: Although sacrament wine is consumed during the Eucharist.

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:
– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:
– No

Are material offerings present:
– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:
– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:
– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:
– Yes

Notes: Candles and flowers.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– I don't know

Notes: Yes and no. There is more social pressure from the community to attend.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– I don't know

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: Also by volunteers from the local community.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

Notes: Ever year, thousands of pilgrims visit. Some arrive on foot, some on horseback, while others come as part of ceremonial cavalcades or cabalgatas

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– I don't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– I don't know

Notes: There are occasional community events held at church.

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: Celebrations for specific Catholic holidays and saint feast days.

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: 200000

Notes: Number of visitors per year, in addition to regular attendants.

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

- Elites
- Non-elites
- Religious professionals

Notes: All can participate.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

- No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

- I don't know

Notes: The priest may ask for God's (or a relevant saint) assistance in helping to heal a member of the community who is ill.

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

- Yes

↳ Present full time

- Yes

↳ Present part time

- Yes

Notes: Volunteers from the local community who assist in church activities.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

- Yes

Notes: Priests are male and the nuns are female.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

- No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

Notes: Although they do tend to serve there for a long time.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Notes: Priests have more authority than nuns.

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: There are living quarters for the priest and a convent for the nuns.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Younger priests and nuns.

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– I don't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

Notes: Franciscan order

- ↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:
 - No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):
– Yes

- ↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Does this place lease out land:
 - No

- ↳ Does this place lease out tools:
 - No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:
– Yes

- ↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:
 - Yes

- ↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):
 - I don't know
 - Notes: But the church may serve as a polling place for the local community.

- ↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):
 - No

- ↳ Function for water management:
 - No

- ↳ Part of the transportation network:
 - No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Local community events

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Catholic scripture.

↳ Are they written at this place:

– No

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: As part of the church services and liturgy.

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

Notes: The history of how Father Kino arrived to the area and proselytized to the local Indigenous populations.

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The priest in charge interprets the scriptures.

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– No